

A Predictive Model for Academic Performance of Students in MAT101 at Federal University Birnin Kebbi

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Abstract:

The research addresses the problem of low academic performance of students taking General Mathematics 1 (MAT101) at the Federal University Birnin Kebbi in Nigeria. MAT101 is a foundational course for several science-related disciplines. However, many students fail to understand its concepts, translating to one of the lowest academic performances, leading to high discontinuation of students' studies in most science and related fields. To this end, the problem is addressed through a predictive model using data science and machine learning techniques to identify students who are academically at risk. It seeks to answer the appropriateness of the selected statistical and data mining approaches, whether or not they

are predictor variables, and validating the model developed. The significance of this study lies in its potential to help instructors identify at-risk students and improve overall performance in MAT101. The research uses data collected from academic records and conducts exploratory data analysis to determine the factors influencing students' performance. Several classifiers such as Decision Tree and Random Forest were analyzed by evaluating their accuracy. In detail, the difference in the accuracy for the Decision Tree algorithm was 52% and for the Random Forest was 67%. Based on achieved indicators, the Random forest algorithm is more effective in this type of predictive modeling. However, the choice of algorithm depends on specific task requirements, considering factors like speed and accuracy.

Keywords: *Predictive modeling, Machine learning, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Academic performance.*

Introduction

Nearly all first year students in science, engineering, environmental studies and college

of health sciences are required to take General Mathematics 1, a foundational first-year subject (Ibrahim, 2004). The course develops students'

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capacity to connect mathematical induction, simple interest, and arithmetic and geometric progression, among other concepts, to the outside world (Huang, 2011). It serves as the foundation for many science courses, including those in Applied Geophysics, Biochemistry, Computer Science, and Industrial Chemistry, among others (Biggers, Orr, & Benson, 2010; Huang, 2010).

Nevertheless, General Mathematics 1 is also regarded as one of the most arduous courses for undergraduates (Self, Wood, & Hansen, 2004). The course requires students to have solid arithmetic skills and a good understanding of fundamental concepts and principles of Mathematics. Many students don't perform well in this course, and some even fail the course.

Despite the important role that Mathematics plays, most students find it challenging to pass and continue it in undergraduate programmes. One of the most frequent causes of this discontinuation and failure in Mathematics immediately draws educators' attention to students' weak secondary Mathematics preparation. While most countries need well-educated people in both traditional and scientific and technical fields—which are crucial for a nation's progress—developed countries have profited much from their population's broad knowledge of education. Education in Mathematics is a cornerstone and essential instrument for every country's growth in science, technology, and economy (Michael & Gold, 2018).

Many other courses/subjects can be understood through the use of Mathematics. In a broad sense, it serves as the foundation for numerous sciences, including astronomy, physics and engineering. The development of and promotion of favourable Mathematical attitudes among students, independent of their cultural and social variations, is necessary to convey such a magnifying, dynamic series of logically based information that includes the development of the hydrogen bomb and compact discs (Ke & Grabowski, 2007).

In an effort to understand the world and ourselves, Mathematics is seen as an essential

component of human intellect and logic. We are aware of how basic Mathematics is, but sadly, it is not taught well in some elementary schools. As a result, Mathematical performance is low, which lowers people's abilities compared to their actual talents (DeCaro, Thomas, Albert, & Beilock, 2011). Females in particular avoid arithmetic in the classroom. This challenge is at its greatest when it is taught by inexperienced and unqualified instructors. The failure of students is eventually evidenced by the fact that attractive and impressive methods are not used to teach Mathematics. Numerous elements, including learner engagement, a lack of trained teachers, inadequate curricula, and the school atmosphere, contribute to students' low Mathematics performance. Lack of student interest, on the other hand, undoubtedly exceeds the capacities of adults and ultimately contributes as one of the most significant determinants for bad performance in Mathematics. Teaching Mathematics is a complex affair (Morales-brendefur & Ed, 2008). On the one hand, learning is quick and instinctual, and on the other, the belief that supports the idea based on working without a strategy and planning for the sake of improving Mathematical abstract and logical fundamental concepts works effectively in most situations. By developing and raising the level of students' interest and involvement, we mean how much time, energy, and effort they devote towards achieving high goals in Mathematics (Morales-brendefur & Ed, 2008).

Our tertiary institutions have seen significant problems with students' performance in General Mathematics 1, also known as MAT 101 at Federal University Birnin Kebbi. There are some significant causes of this issue. Due to this new development, several experts are now focusing on deciphering and predicting students' academic performance. Using the results of a predictive model, university instructors can implement important strategies to enhance learning, especially for students performing below average (Davison & Smith, 2018). In recent years, data science and machine learning have played a significant role in enhancing students' academic performance in post-secondary institutions.

Data science and machine learning have become increasingly effective and tenacious over time in numerous industries, including education. Data science is a multidisciplinary field that works with both structured and unstructured data, drawing information and insights from the data utilizing scientific methods, procedures, algorithms, and systems. Data mining and big data are both parts of data science (Huang, 2011).

An area of artificial intelligence (AI) is machine learning. It permits a computing system to learn from data and create significant predictions within development businesses that are looking for creative approaches to use data assets to support the business's advancement to a new level. Applications of machine learning include, but are not limited to, pattern and image identification, fraud detection, equipment failure prediction, student performance prediction, weather forecasting, and failure prediction (Kabakchieva, 2012).

Materials and Methods

To predict academic performance of students, a range of methods are used. Some of these methods are data mining and conventional mathematical models. These methods describe the quantitative relationships between the inputs and outputs using a series of mathematical formulas (i.e. dependent and independent variables). In this research, Decision Tree and Random Forest classifiers were the methods utilized to extract knowledge from the student's performance dataset. The research technique is shown in Figure 1.

Data Mining Process

Python was used to develop the predictive model. Python is a language frequently employed in applications involving machine learning. The approach chosen for this research has built-in libraries for it. These built-in libraries help to generate the appropriate output for the predictions. Jupyter Notebook was used to run the Python programs. The data gathered was stored in a Microsoft Excel Comma Separated Values File (.csv) format with the features

specified. But the names and student admission numbers were not included for confidential reasons. The dataset was cleaned to remove duplicates, incomplete data and unnecessary symbols (such as spaces, commas, and colons).

Following that, five phases of data modeling stage were implored: training, pattern, testing, result evaluation, and knowledge representation. Additionally, Decision Tree and Random Forest were used to predict students' performance in General Mathematics 1 (MAT 101).

Figure 1. Proposed Methodology

Performance Metrics

Confusion Matrix

The structure of a confusion matrix is such that the predictions are represented by the columns, while the actual class is represented by the rows. The diagonal of the matrix always shows the accurate predictions. Here is the standard format of a confusion matrix.

The True Positives (TP) in a classification scenario represents the correct predictions of the minority class, whereas the True Negatives (TN) represents the correct predictions of the majority class. False Positives (FP) refer to the instances of the majority class that were mistakenly classified as minority class, while False Negatives (FN) indicate the minority class instances that were classified as majority class instances. While the confusion matrix provides a more comprehensive picture of the classifier's

performance than accuracy, it's recommended to use additional metrics for more detailed analysis.

Table 1. Standard Classification of Confusion Matrix

		Actual Label	
		Positive	Negative
Predicted Label	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
	Negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

Results

Data Collection and Data Cleaning

The data used for this research was students' academic data from faculty of science, environmental sciences and school of nursing sciences of Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. The size of the data is 207 comprising of 129 males and 78 females. The data consist of a set of graduated and undergraduate students. The data was collected through a Google form questionnaire between November 2022 and December 2022. The questionnaire was shared across the faculties and departmental WhatsApp groups and other social media handles of the university. The grading system in Federal University Birnin Kebbi is a letter grade ranging from A to F. These grades are based on a numeric 5-point scale where A is equivalent to 5 points representing excellent and F is equivalent to 0 point representing very poor performance. The distribution of the grades of the students sampled is contained in Figure 2.

The O'Level Mathematics Grade (WAEC, NECO and NABTEB), Gender, JAMB Maths Score, and Total JAMB Score were used as input parameters to predict their Grades in General Mathematics 1 also known as MAT 101 in Federal University Birnin Kebbi.

Figure 2. The Distribution of the Grades of Student's Sample

Source: Author's own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023.

The preparation of the dataset for model building is the first step taken. At this point, conventional pre-processing techniques such as data cleaning, variable modification, and data segmentation were used. In order to address the issues of value error, 2 Dimensional array was used in reshaping and indexing the NumPy array and imbalanced data that may be present in the dataset. Other strategies including characteristics selection and rebalancing of data were also used.

The size of the training and test subgroups were configured as the primary parameter during the training and testing of the dataset. This typically represents the percentage of data assigned to each subset as a number between 0 and 1. For instance, if the size of the training dataset is 0.67 (67%) it would follow that the test dataset would receive the remaining 0.33 (33%) of the dataset's size.

It is important to note that there isn't a single optimal split percentage because it depends on the size, composition, and goals of the dataset.

Nevertheless, the split percentage used for this research is shown in the table below;

Table 2. Split Percentage

Train (%)	Test (%)
90	10

Exploratory Data Analysis

Figure 3 below shows that some students were assisted during their O’level examination. It is our belief that any form of malpractice or assistance rendered to students during their O’level Mathematics Examination could affect their performance in MAT101 at Federal University Birnin Kebbi.

Figure 3. Proportion of the Students Who were Helped or Not during their O’level

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023.

Figure 4. Proportion of Students Who were Helped or Not during their JAMB Examination

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023.

Figure 5. Count of Students Who Either Sat for His/Her Examination or Not

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023

Performance of Each Classifier

Multiple experiments were undertaken to determine the efficiency of each algorithm in forecasting students' academic performance. Various performance metrics, including prediction accuracy, precision, and recall, were used to evaluate the predictive performance of each classifier. Table 3 presents a summary of the outcome obtained in each experiment.

Table 3. Prediction Performance of each Classifier

Metric Evaluation	Classifier	
	Decision Tree	Random Forest
Accuracy	52%	67%
Precision	0.77	0.92
Recall	0.67	0.75
F-Measure	0.71	0.83
Support	15	16

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023

The table below shows the time complexity in milliseconds of various classifiers to build the model for training data.

Table 4. Execution Time to Build the Model

Algorithm	Execution Time (ms)
Decision Tree	7.5
Random Forest	13.5

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023

To gain a deeper comprehension of the importance of individual variables in the Random Forest Classifier's output variable, an evaluation was conducted to assess the effect of each variable on the accuracy of student prediction. As illustrated in figure 7, it shows that JAMB Maths Score is the most significant feature in our classification model.

Figure 6. Feature Importance of the Model

Source: Author’s own computation using Jupyter notebook, May, 2023.

The figure below shows the confusion matrix for Random forest classifier. This means all the values on the diagonal are correctly classified while the ones off diagonal are misclassified.

Table 5. Confusion Matrix for Decision Tree

Confusion Matrix for Decision Tree				
0	2	0	0	0
3	10	2	0	0
0	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0

Table 6. Confusion Matrix for Random Forest

Confusion Matrix for Random Forests			
2	1	1	0
1	12	0	0
0	3	0	0
0	0	1	0

Discussion

The Decision Tree algorithm and Random Forest algorithm are both widely used for classification and regression tasks in machine learning. Here is a detailed discussion and conclusion on these two algorithms based on this research.

Mean Squared Error

The mean squared error (MSE) is a measure of how well the algorithm is performing on the regression task. The lower the mean squared error, the better the performance of the algorithm. In this research, the random forest algorithm has a lower MSE of 0.619 compared to the decision tree algorithm's MSE of 0.761. This shows that our random forest algorithm has prediction than the decision tree algorithm.

Execution Time

The execution time is a measure of how long the algorithm takes to process the data. In this research, the decision tree algorithm has a shorter execution time of 7.5 milliseconds compared to the random forest algorithm's execution time of 13.5 milliseconds. This means that the decision tree algorithm is faster than the random forest algorithm.

Accuracy

The accuracy is a measure of how well the algorithm is performing on the classification task. The higher the accuracy, the better the performance of the algorithm. In this study, the random forest algorithm has a higher accuracy of 67% compared to the decision tree algorithm's accuracy of 52%. This shows that the random forest algorithm is better suited for the classification tasks than the decision tree algorithm.

Precision

Precision is a measure of the proportion of true positives among all the predicted positive cases. In this study, the random forest algorithm has a higher precision of 0.92 compared to the decision tree algorithm's precision of 0.77. This means that the random forest algorithm is better at predicting positive cases.

Recall

Recall is a measure of the proportion of true positives among the actual positive cases. In this research, the random forest algorithm has a higher recall of 0.75 compared to the decision tree algorithm's recall of 0.67. This indicates that the random forest algorithm is better at identifying actual positive cases.

F-Measure

The F-Measure is a measure of the harmonic mean of precision and recall. In this study, the random forest algorithm has a higher F-Measure of 0.83 compared to the decision tree algorithm's F-Measure of 0.71. This shows that the random forest algorithm is better suited for classification tasks than the decision tree algorithm.

Based on the dataset used for this research, the random forest algorithm outperforms the decision tree algorithm in most of the measures such as MSE, accuracy, precision, recall, and F-Measure. However, the decision tree algorithm is faster in execution time. Therefore, the choice of algorithm depends on the specific requirements of the task at hand. If speed is a priority, then the decision tree algorithm may be a better choice. However, if accuracy is a priority,

then the random forest algorithm may be a better choice.

Conclusion

The educational field utilizes Data Mining to gain a better understanding of the learning process by identifying, extracting, and evaluating variables related to students' academic performance. As many universities and colleges require a strong science background for prospective Mathematics candidates, this research investigates the impact of science subjects on their academic performance. To predict their performance in General Mathematics 1 (MAT101), student information such as Gender, O'level Grades, JAMB Maths Score, and JAMB Score were collected through a questionnaire, and the classification task was used to evaluate their performance. In this study, Decision Tree and Random Forest models were used to classify the data, as they are popular for producing easy-to-interpret classification rules.

Data Mining is becoming increasingly popular in various real-world applications, and classification, as a data mining technique, is an area of interest to researchers for its ability to accurately and efficiently classify data for knowledge discovery. To find the best classifier for student data, Decision Tree and Random Forest classifiers are frequently studied, and experiments are conducted. Based on the dataset used in this research, our experiment indicates that Random Forest is the best algorithm for classification.

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